

Enabling Navigability of Programming Language Specifications

A Case of ECMAScript (JavaScript) Standard Library Specification

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Abstract

Many widely adopted programming languages (e.g., C++, Java, JavaScript, WebAssembly) have specification documents that provide authoritative answers about the language and its semantics. However, such specification documents are often-times demanding to read and navigate. This especially manifests when a text, a PDF, or an HTML document describes the language semantics using a pseudo-code notation—which is treated as text rather than code. Readers of a language specification are thus left without any dedicated tool support to navigate the pseudo-code.

In this paper, we propose to tackle the lack of navigability in programming language specification documents by implementing their “*IDE twins*”, which mimic the notation used in such documents and provide advanced navigation-related functionality, such as pseudo-code querying or manipulating the abstract syntax tree of the specification document.

To enable this advanced functionality, we formalize the notion of a *navigation-aware specification document*, and present a domain-specific language for expressing *navigation tasks*, which allow filtering a specification document and “injecting” navigation-related marks into it. Navigation tasks and their results become thus persisted and shareable. The design of our navigation DSL is agnostic of the pseudo-code notation of a particular language specification.

We showcase the feasibility of our approach by implementing, in the language workbench JetBrains MPS, an IDE twin for a fragment of the JavaScript specification document that covers the standard library of the language and accounts for more than 440 pages of the 847-page document. We discuss how the navigation DSL, which we compose with the pseudo-code language of the specification, can be used to navigate this fragment and inform the evolution process of JavaScript.

CCS Concepts: • General and reference → Computing standards, RFCs and guidelines; • Software and its engineering → General programming languages; Documentation; Domain specific languages; Collaboration in software development.

Keywords: Widely adopted languages, code navigation, language specification, language workbenches, domain-specific languages.

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1 Introduction

Over the past decades, the entry barrier to design and specify a new software language has lowered: language design and implementation support tools—known as *language workbenches* [27]—provide a streamlined way to define the syntax of a language, as well as allow expressing its semantics, and in some cases do so in a succinct (and declarative) manner [8, 73, 81, 89]. The produced Integrated Development Environments (IDEs) provide industry-level tool support for the language, including rich editor services [27, 112], debuggers [66], among other functionality. Language workbenches have become a *de facto* standard way to implement domain-specific languages [112], as was envisioned by Fowler [32] and Dmitriev [21]. Implementing a domain-specific language goes beyond purely technical artifacts though: successful language adoption assumes various non-technical artifacts to be provided to language users [13, 55, 80, 112]. One example of such an artifact is language documentation [13, 55, 88], which can take form of, for instance, a user manual, a language reference, or a “cookbook”, which describes language features and showcases how they can be used.

For *widely adopted* general-purpose programming¹ languages, with millions of daily users, language documentation becomes even more important, as it provides authoritative answers about the language and its semantics. Whenever a language is mature enough to have more than one implementation, a need for a more formal *specification*—or even a *standard* [31]—arises. This allows multiple language implementations to be consistent with each other *and* with the language specification. The question of whether a language *should* have a specification or a standard (or none at

¹Even though we use the term “programming languages” throughout the paper, our approach is in principle applicable to any widely adopted software language with a specified standard library (for example, CSS [115]).

all) is tightly connected to language governance [46], and various language design teams have answered this question differently. For example, C++ [43], Fortran [44], Ada [45], Dart [25], Scheme [42], WebAssembly [114], JavaScript [23] are standardized by international standardization bodies—ISO, IEEE, W3C, Ecma International—and their specifications are formal documents conforming to the relevant bodies' publication requirements. Python [104], Java [103], Go [102], and Swift [106], among many others, have specification documents, but not official (normative) standards. Some languages, such as Rust, prefer to have an informal reference manual [105] and a reference implementation. In this paper, we focus on languages that either have a (semi-)formal specification document or a standard published by a recognized body. We will refer to either of these artifacts as *specification documents*.

A specification document must provide a precise (ideally, unambiguous) definition of a language, including its syntax, and—to a known extent—its semantics. It is safe to assume that syntax will (or at least *can*) be specified formally, for instance, by means of a variant of the Backus-Naur-Form [119]. As for semantics, its “precision” varies from inference rules in the case of ML [71] or WebAssembly [114], to informal natural language prose in the case of Fortran [44] or Java [103]. A specification document should be accessible to its target audience—be it language implementors, users, educators, designers, or other groups. This prompts specification authors to find ways to incorporate various notations in a single document: for example, the syntax and semantics of WebAssembly are specified in a formal way using a tailored DSL [118], and the specification document, which is automatically *generated* from code in this DSL, defines the language's dynamic semantics using inference rules *and* (implementor-friendly) algorithmic prose. Other languages, such as JavaScript [23], define their semantics using a semi-formal pseudo-code notation, which essentially provides a (non-executable²) reference implementation for the language.

Most of the existing language specifications are static documents (e.g., PDF files [43, 44, 103]) of a significant size (more than 2100 pages for the C++ standard [43]). This makes *navigating* these documents a difficult task—as it assumes an understanding of a particular jargon (so-called “standardese” [3]) and the knowledge of how the document is structured. In addition, the pseudo-code notation—if it is used to describe the semantics of the language—is represented merely as *text* in a static document.

Some of the languages that use pseudo-code notation in their specifications, such as JavaScript or WebAssembly, have addressed this problem by making their specification documents interactive [23, 114–116]. A specification becomes an

²The pseudo-code notation used in the JavaScript specification has been found to be “formal enough” to automatically derive a reference implementation [83] from it.

HTML document, with support for only the most basic navigation functionality such as “go to definition” (implemented via HTML `<a>` tags). In this paper, *we propose to tackle the lack of advanced navigability in a programming language specification document by employing software language engineering, i.e., by implementing a language that mimics the notation of the document, and providing IDE support for it.*

Having an IDE support for a specification document allows us to explore further functionality related to navigating such documents; this functionality is motivated by existing empirical studies on code navigation and comprehension (e.g., [14, 18, 33, 34, 60, 62, 74, 90, 93, 108, 121]). Our implementation is done in language workbench JetBrains MPS [49], and many of these navigation-related features are provided out-of-the-box (e.g., “go to definition”, “find usages”, “diff”, etc.) With the projectional editor³ of MPS, we can replicate the notation of the specification document; one can think of this as an “IDE twin” of a language specification (complementary to *hyperlinked twins* [72] that provide web-based navigable representations for language definitions).

Navigating a codebase oftentimes requires performing a (structural) search on it [20]. To enable this, we introduce a domain-specific language (DSL) for expressing *navigation tasks*, which allow filtering a specification document, “injecting” navigation-related marks into it (e.g., remarks, decorations, and so on), and invoking code editor commands. The design of our navigation DSL is agnostic of the notation of a particular specification document.

We demonstrate the feasibility of our approach on a fragment of the JavaScript (formally, ECMAScript) specification document [23] that defines its standard library algorithms, and accounts for more than 440 pages in the 847-page document. We also discuss how our approach can be used to inform the very process of JavaScript language *evolution*, where members of the language design committee who review new feature specifications—by manually searching and navigating the current specification document—could benefit from tool support.

2 Navigability of Specification Documents

Considering C++ [43] and JavaScript [23] as examples, one can observe that recently more additions have been made to the *standard libraries* of these languages than to their syntax [53, 100]. Such widely adopted languages are very mature, have a very limited available “syntax budget” [99], and thus focus on enriching their standard libraries, which could be attributed to the success of these languages [37, 69, 96, 117]. One can also hypothesize that a language's standard library is the most developer-oriented fragment of a programming language specification document.

³We envision our tool to be used for reading the specification document, not for authoring it—hence many issues with projectional editing, such as linear input of tree structures [113], are not directly relevant in our case.

We note that the mechanisms of how standard library functions and their canonical implementations are specified, differ across languages [52]. For example, C++ specification document [43] briefly describes (in a natural language) the machinery of a function, specifies pre- and post-conditions, and discusses some corner cases of its implementation. Similarly, Fortran specification document [44] informally describes a function, its arguments, and the resulting value, as well as gives examples. Java [103] and Kotlin [61] specification documents provide only very brief explanations of standard library functions, and mention examples of how they are used. None of these specification documents provide complete algorithms that can be directly used to implement the standard library in an independent language implementation. This is in contrast with the JavaScript specification document [23], which specifies, using a highly normalized pseudo-code, all of its standard library functions and their implementations. WebAssembly specification document [114] is unique in that the language semantics is specified using pseudo-code which is *generated* from a formal inference rules specification [118], rather than manually written.

Specification documents are oftentimes quite demanding to read, as can be exemplified by the existence of guides for developers on how to read language specifications and standards (cf., e.g., [3, 16, 35, 51]). Navigating a specification document provides an even bigger challenge for a reader: oftentimes [25, 42–45, 102, 103, 106] a specification is a static document (e.g., a plain text file, a rich text document, or a PDF file). While these static documents are printer-friendly, and thus are preferred by—archival oriented—standardization bodies, *language users have no dedicated tool support when reading or navigating them.*

Some major software languages, especially in the web space, provide interactivity in their specification documents, e.g., JavaScript [23], WebAssembly [114], CSS [115], HTML [116], among others. For JavaScript, for example, the specification document is an interactive web-application that provides *some* navigation support: basic syntax highlighting, outline view, “go to definition”, “find usages”, free-text search, pinning parts of the document, as well as toggling special annotations for implementors [30]. A third-party tool maintained by an individual developer [26] additionally provides support for the “diff” feature. The implementation of the mentioned functionality is primarily based on web technologies, and thus the pseudo-code in the document is still treated as *text*, not as a first-class citizen—*code*. This means that the current perspectives on code reading, such as that code “should” be read in a dedicated tool (cf., e.g., [84]), are not applicable to language specification documents, yet these documents indirectly form a foundation for software systems.

In this paper, we treat programming language specification documents as first-class citizens, and advocate for implementing feature-rich IDE support for reading and navigating them. We call such tools *IDE twins of specification documents.*

We now identify functionality that an IDE twin of a specification document should have, and we especially focus on functionality related to reading the pseudo-code notation used to define standard library algorithms. We cite relevant empirical studies that discuss usefulness of such features for navigation and comprehension of “ordinary” code.

We categorize the functionality into three groups: (i) navigation of the entire specification document, (ii) within an individual algorithm pseudo-code, (iii) advanced navigation.

Navigation of the entire document. *Outline view* [74] visualizes the structure of a specification document while respecting its structural units (e.g., “sections”, “subsections”, etc.) *Free-text search* [20] in the outline view allows filtering relevant structural units of the specification document. *Cloning* the entire specification document creates local copies [85] of the specification that can be modified by a reader by means of *renaming* [33], *rearranging* [90], or *removing* [107] structural units, individual algorithms, or their fragments. The IDE twin of a specification document should, where applicable, support *navigating back* to a relevant part of *the original (normative) specification document.*

Navigation within an algorithm. *Go to definition* [74] and *Find usages* [74] enable navigating to an entity’s declaration and exploring references to it, in a bidirectional manner. *Highlight occurrences* stylizes all occurrences of a currently selected entity within an algorithm. *Rename refactoring* as a mechanism to facilitate code comprehension [33, 41] allows renaming an entity in a user’s local copy of the specification document. *Free-text search* within an algorithm allows navigating to a particular entity or an entity fragment. *Add a tag* and *add a remark* to an entire algorithm or a step of an algorithm allow creating reader-defined beacons [14] that help the reader construct a mental model of the specification document [60, 68, 93, 108]. *Adapt to the reader* [75] allows changing the pseudo-code notation used in an algorithm to cater to various reader categories (for instance, a more succinct notation will be shown for experts, while a more verbose one for novice readers). *Adapt to stylistic preferences* [76], in a similar way, enables modifying fine-grained characteristics of the pseudo-code notation (e.g., indentation). *Inline an algorithm* (cf. “peek” in VSCode) allows showing (in a recursive manner) the pseudo-code of an algorithm A' , which is referenced from within an algorithm A , directly in the pseudo-code of the algorithm A . This enables reading the code for both of the algorithms in a single editor tab (cf. [18, 60]).

Advanced navigation. Given two algorithms, *diff* [40] enables “parallel reading” of these algorithms and visually highlighting and locating their differences. This could be used to compare either two semantically relevant algorithms (e.g., implementation of addition and subtraction on a certain number type), or algorithms that are supposed to be structurally similar (e.g., allocating an array buffer vs. allocating a shared array buffer).

For experienced readers, *displaying the abstract syntax tree* of an algorithm or a step of an algorithm provides a detailed overview of the concepts of the specification language—i.e., the pseudo-code notation itself.

Querying [2, 20, 67] (sometimes referred to as *filtering* or *structural search* [4, 63]) the pseudo-code allows specifying a query against the entirety of the pseudo-code of a specification document, with the goal to only focus on those algorithms, or their steps, that match the query. Ideally, patterns mentioned in such queries can use the pseudo-code notation [5, 6] of the specification document. *Decorating* query results allows marking and tailoring [14, 18, 34] relevant parts of the specification document (e.g., adding a remark or a tag to all algorithms that match a query, highlighting a matching step with a background of a certain color, etc.) A particular example of decorating is *pruning* [18, 107] of pseudo-code, which allows modifying a copy of a specification document to focus a reader’s attention only on parts that are relevant to their current navigation session. Executing commands of the *code editor* [60, 121] allows introducing automatization of navigation-related tasks (e.g., opening code editor tabs for the algorithms of interest). A special case of this is *grouping* [90] of algorithms, which allows rearranging the specification document so that relevant—as defined by the reader—algorithms would be visually shown in a same group in the outline view. *Aggregating* [2] of query results allows presenting reports with summary-like information about the algorithms that match certain criteria (e.g., the amount of algorithms with particular names of formal parameters). *Persisting the query* and *persisting query results* [4, 77, 85, 87] allow storing and re-running a query at a later point, as well as enable collaborative [7, 11, 19, 34] navigation by several readers. Usual IDE functionality should apply to queries and query results (e.g., *go to definition*, *diff*, and so on). It should also be possible to perform *composition* [50] of navigation-related tasks; this enables complex navigation pipelines.

Finally, *exposing the abstract syntax tree of the specification document* gives readers an ultimate control to perform arbitrary manipulation of the specification document [109].

We present in Figure 1 a feature model for IDE twins of programming language specification documents. \square

To enable rich navigation functionality described above, we design a domain-specific language that allows expressing navigation-related tasks. We introduce this language in the next section, and give code samples in Section 4.3.

3 A Domain-Specific Language to Define Navigation Pipelines

We formalize the notions of a navigation-aware specification document and of a navigation task over such documents. Based on these definitions, we design a domain-specific language that allows expressing navigation tasks in programming language specification documents.

3.1 Specification Documents and Navigation Tasks

We start by defining the notion of a navigation-aware specification document.

Definition 3.1. A *specification document* is a 5-tuple $D = \langle \mathcal{U}, \mathcal{A}, P, S, F \rangle$, where \mathcal{U} is a collection of structural units (e.g., “parts”, “sections”, “subsections”) of the document, \mathcal{A} is a collection of algorithms that define the language’s semantics, written using a pseudo-code notation P , and S is the definition of language’s syntax written in a syntax specification formalism F .

In what follows, we will only focus on the algorithms in the standard library of a language, and we ignore components S and F of the tuple. We will thus denote specification documents as triples $D = \langle \mathcal{U}, \mathcal{A}, P \rangle$.

We can now define the concept of a navigation-aware algorithm.

Definition 3.2. Let $D = \langle \mathcal{U}, \mathcal{A}, P \rangle$ be a specification document. An *algorithm* $A \in \mathcal{A}$ is defined as a quadruple $A = \langle U, \sigma, C, \Omega \rangle$, where $U \in \mathcal{U}$ is the structural unit of the specification document where the algorithm resides, σ is the algorithm’s signature, C is a collection of its steps, and Ω is a set of *navigation annotations* introduced by a user while reading and navigating the algorithm. A navigation annotation $\omega \in \Omega$ is defined as a tuple $\omega = \langle R, e \rangle$, where R is a record expressing its properties, and $e \in \sigma \cup C$ is the target element to which this annotation has been attached (either algorithm’s signature or a step of the algorithm).

We now demonstrate these definitions.

Example 3.3. The JavaScript specification document “ECMA-262” [23] can be denoted as $D_{262} = \langle \mathcal{U}_{262}, \mathcal{A}_{262}, P_{262} \rangle$, where \mathcal{U}_{262} contains section numbers (such as “1”, “2.1”, “9.3.2”, “B.1.2.8.1”), \mathcal{A}_{262} is a collection of built-in functions and abstract operations⁴, and P_{262} is the pseudo-code notation defined in §5.2 “Algorithm Conventions” of the document.

An example of an algorithm is $A_{\text{BigInt}::\text{add}} = \langle 6.1.6.2.7, \{x, y\}, \{(@1, \text{ReturnStep}(\text{Plus}(x, y)))\}, \emptyset \rangle$. This algorithm, defined in §6.1.6.2.7 of the specification document [23], specifies function $\text{BigInt}::\text{add}$ with two parameters x and y . The body of this function has a single step, which is a return statement with the expression $x + y$. The set Ω is empty, meaning that the reader of the specification document has not left any navigation-related annotations.

When reading the specification document, the reader may make a copy of this algorithm, add a tag to its name, and then add a free-text remark onto the first step of the (copied) algorithm and prune (i.e., hide) this step. The set Ω' of this copy $A'_{\text{BigInt}::\text{add}}$ would then be defined as $\{\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3\}$, with $\omega_1 = \langle \text{TAG}(\text{“one-liner”}), \text{BigInt}::\text{add} \rangle$, $\omega_2 = \langle \text{REMARK}(\text{“Semantics was here.”}), @1 \rangle$, and $\omega_3 = \langle \text{PRUNE}(), @1 \rangle$. Here $@1$ denotes the first step of the algorithm. \square

⁴We explain the difference between these in Section 4.1.

Figure 1. A feature model of an IDE twin of a specification document. While the list of features is non-exhaustive, the key representatives of various feature categories, as discussed in Section 2, are present.

We are now ready to define the notion of a navigation task, which will be instrumental in the design of our DSL.

Definition 3.4. A *navigation task* is defined as a 6-tuple $N = \langle D_{in}, D_{out}, N_{filter}, N_{decorate}, N_{editor}, N_{aggregate} \rangle$, where D_{in} is the specification document on which the navigation task is executed, D_{out} is the specification document which will be produced as a result of executing the navigation task, N_{filter} is a collection of *filtering templates*, $N_{decorate}$ is a collection of *decorating actions*, N_{edit} is a collection of *code editor actions*, and $N_{aggregate}$ is a collection of *aggregating actions*.

3.2 DSL for Specifying Navigation Tasks

Our DSL uses the following syntax⁵ to define a navigation task $N = \langle D_{in}, D_{out}, N_{filter}, N_{decorate}, N_{editor}, N_{aggregate} \rangle$.

```

navigation <identifier>
  input-document <identifier>
  output-document <identifier>
  filter
  // filtering templates (0..n)
    
```

⁵The actual concrete syntax of our DSL employs the rich syntax notation of a projectional editor to improve the ergonomics of the language.

```

decorate
  // decorating actions (0..n)
code-editor
  // code editor actions (0..n)
report
  // aggregation actions (0..n)
    
```

This code specifies the task’s identifier and the identifiers of the input (D_{in}) and the output (D_{out}) documents. The machinery of a navigation is specified in four (optional) blocks filter, decorate, code-editor, and report, which correspond to N_{filter} , $N_{decorate}$, N_{editor} , and $N_{aggregate}$, respectively. To facilitate code reuse, the code of any block can be extracted into a standalone snippet, which can be then referenced from a navigation task (e.g., filter MyFilteringBlock).

Below we describe each of the blocks in detail.

Filtering templates

The filter-block defines a collection $N_{filter} = \{f_1, \dots, f_n\}$ of individual *filtering templates*.

A filtering template $f : \mathcal{A}_{in}^* \times Q \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_{in}^*$ is executed against the entire specification document D_{in} , and it matches all algorithms $A = \langle U, \sigma, C, \Omega \rangle \in \mathcal{A}_{in}$ that satisfy the filtering

condition Q . This condition is a Boolean predicate on either of: an algorithm location U in D_{in} , an algorithm signature σ , an algorithm body C , or navigation annotations Ω left by a reader while reading an algorithm.

Filtering templates are specified in our DSL as follows.

```

556 1 filter <identifier>
557 2     either [not] <template>
558 3     or // ...
559 4     or // ...
560 5     // more templates in the disjunction
561 6 and
562 7     // ...
563 8 and
564 9     // more either-or blocks

```

A filtering block is thus a product of sums of filtering templates (i.e., it is defined using the conjunctive normal form). Boolean negation is represented by the optional not keyword prepending a template.

Filtering templates on an *algorithm location* include: regular expressions on the title of a structural unit, the number of a structural unit, the identifier of the structural unit as specified in the original specification document. These can be specified in our DSL as follows.

```

576 1 location // appears in a filter-block
577 2     section-title <regexp>
578 3     section-number <regexp>
579 4     section-id <regexp>

```

Filtering templates on an *algorithm signature* include: algorithm's name, number of formal parameters, presence of a formal parameter with a certain name or a certain category (e.g., ordinary, optional, variadic), among others⁶. This can be defined in our DSL using the following syntax.

```

586 1 signature // appears in a filter-block
587 2     name <regexp>
588 3     number-of-params <integer>
589 4     has-param-with-name <regexp>
590 5     // more properties

```

Filtering templates on an *algorithm body* are the basis of the structural search on the specification document, and can be specified using the following specification-aware syntax (in terms of [28, 112], the formalism of the specification document is a language *embedded* in our DSL).

```

597 1 body // appears in a filter-block
598 2     contains <quotation>

```

The quotation specified in a contains-clause allows quoting compound steps, individual steps, or fragments of individual steps of algorithms, *using the notation of the specification*

⁶We present in this section the most relevant representatives of the built-in primitives of our DSL, without giving an exhaustive list of all of them.

document. The algorithms in the specification document will be then matched against the code pattern specified in the quotation. In a quoted fragment, omitted parts are treated as wildcards, and specified parts are matched exactly. As an example, the quotation `[Let \square be \square .]` will match all algorithms that have a let-step with any name of the variable and any assigned expression, whereas the quotation `[Let x be \square .]` will only match those cases when the name of the variable is x . We showcase less trivial quotations, including step fragments (e.g., accessing an array element) and compound steps (e.g., a loop statement), in Section 4. We note that compound quotations may use “abstract steps”—which match any step—to define wildcard-like structural patterns.

Filtering templates on *navigation annotations* include: checking whether a tag or a remark has been attached to a step of an algorithm, or to an algorithm as a whole; checking whether a step has been pruned (either manually or as a result of a previously executed navigation task⁷); checking whether a step has been highlighted with a particular color (again, either manually or as a result of a previous task), and so on.

Our DSL uses the following syntax for these.

```

491 annotations // appears in a filter-block
492     has-tag <string>
493     has-remark <string>
494     has-pruned-step
495     has-highlighted-step [<color>]
496     // more annotations

```

Decorating actions

The decorate-block defines a collection $N_{\text{decorate}} = \{d_1, \dots, d_n\}$ of decorating actions of the form $d : \mathcal{A}_{\text{in}} \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_{\text{in}}$. Each of them attaches a navigation annotation to an element of an algorithm specification.

Examples of decorating actions include: adding (or removing) a tag or a remark, pruning or unpruning steps of an algorithm, highlighting or unhighlighting steps with a background of a certain color, and so on.

The following syntax is used in our DSL for specifying decorating actions.

```

497 decorate <identifier>
498     add-tag <string>
499     remove-tag <string>
500     add-remark <string>
501     remove-remarks
502     prune
503     unprune
504     highlight <color>
505     remove-highlighting [<color>]
506     // more decorating actions

```

⁷This is explained in details in the rest of this section.

Decorating actions—being a mechanism to add navigation annotations to algorithms—can be applied to steps that match the filtering templates specified in the `filter-block`, or to an algorithm as a whole (i.e., to its signature).

Code editor actions

The `code-editor-block` defines a collection $N_{\text{editor}} = \{t_1, \dots, t_n\}$ of code editor actions of the form $t : \mathcal{A}_{\text{in}} \times \Theta \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_{\text{in}} \times \Theta$. Here Θ represents the state of the IDE twin (e.g., the content of the outline view, the list of the open editor tabs, etc.)

Possible code editor actions include: renaming an algorithm (by adding a prefix and a suffix to its current name); removing steps (rather than pruning them); inlining the pseudo-code of all called algorithms; rearranging the outline view in the IDE (by moving algorithms to virtual “folders”); opening new tabs with pseudo-code of algorithms (and additionally tweaking that view, e.g., as a grid).

Our DSL uses the following syntax to specify navigation-related code editor actions.

```

1 code-editor <identifier>
2   rename-algorithm <string> <string>
3   inline-algorithm-calls
4   put-into-folder <string>
5   open-all-in-separate-tabs
6   // more code editor actions

```

Similarly to decorating actions, code editor actions are applied to targets that match filtering templates specified in the `filter-block`.

Aggregating actions

Finally, the `report-block` defines a collection of aggregating actions $N_{\text{aggregate}} = \{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$ of the form $a : \mathcal{A}_{\text{in}}^* \rightarrow V$. Here elements of the set V represent *values*, which are pieces of information obtained by performing a reduce-like operation on algorithms in a specification document.

Examples of aggregating actions include: a list of all algorithms that match a filtering template, a sorted version of this list, the total count of such algorithms, the average number of steps in them, and so on.

The syntax of our DSL is as follows.

```

1 report <identifier>
2   count
3   show-section-number
4   sort-by-name
5   sort-by-number-of-params
6   // more aggregating actions

```

Composition of navigation tasks. Given two navigation tasks $N = \langle D_{\text{in}}, D_{\text{out}}, N_{\text{filter}}, N_{\text{decorate}}, N_{\text{editor}}, N_{\text{aggregate}} \rangle$ and $N' = \langle D'_{\text{in}}, D'_{\text{out}}, N'_{\text{filter}}, N'_{\text{decorate}}, N'_{\text{editor}}, N'_{\text{aggregate}} \rangle$, their composition $N \circ N'$ can be expressed in our DSL by specifying two navigation-blocks as follows.

```

1 navigation N
2   input-document D_in
3   output-document D_out
4   // ...
5
6 navigation N'
7   input-document D'_out
8   output-document D'_out
9   // ...

```

Here the output of the navigation task N is used as the input of the navigation task N' , i.e., $D'_{\text{in}} \equiv D_{\text{out}}$.

We refer to a composition of several navigation tasks as a *navigation pipeline*. We note that in a general case, composition of navigation tasks is not commutative⁸. □

We outline the machinery of our DSL in Appendix A.

4 Case Study

We describe in this section an IDE twin we have implemented for the fragment of the JavaScript specification document that defines the standard library of the language. We also showcase how our DSL can be used to navigate this library.

4.1 The JavaScript Specification Document

The JavaScript (ECMAScript) specification document, officially known as ECMA-262 [23], is maintained by the Technical Committee 39 (TC39) of Ecma International. The structure of the document is defined by 29 sections, each of which has several nested levels of subsections. The content of the document includes clauses that define: *rules of the grammar* of the language, *syntax-directed operations* that define semantics of the grammar rules, *built-in functions* that specify the methods of built-in objects of the language, and *abstract operations* which are not exposed to language users, but are defined to facilitate the specification of the syntax-directed operations and the built-in functions. In this paper, we focus on the built-in functions and the abstract operations, which we collectively refer to as *the standard library algorithms*. The document has 1101 such algorithms.

These algorithms are specified using a pseudo-code notation, which is (partially) described in §5.2 of the document. It is important to underline that this notation is **not** related to the syntax of the JavaScript language itself. It uses various specification-document-only concepts, such as “mathematical operations”, “records”, “enums”, “relations”, “lists”, as well as special shorthands for some of them. The pseudo-code uses well-known control flow primitives (e.g., conditionals, loops), local variables, function calls, assertions, and so on.

⁸Indeed, consider task N that unprunes all steps in all algorithms of the input document. Consider another task N' that prunes all steps of algorithms that match some filtering template f . Then $N \circ N'$ would unprune all steps and then prune those that match f , whereas $N' \circ N$ would do the pruning first, and then unprune all steps. As a result, in the first case the steps that match f will be still pruned, while in the second case no steps will be pruned.

```

771 7.1.6 ToInt32(argument)
772 1. Let number be ? ToNumber(argument).
773 [Abstract Operation]
774 7.1.4 ToNumber(argument)
775 1. If argument is a Number, Return argument.
776 2. Pruned away.
777 3. If argument is undefined, Return NaN.
778 4. If argument is either null or false, Return +0.
779 5. If argument is true, Return 1.
780 6. If argument is a String, Return StringToNumber(argument).
781 7. Assert: argument is an Object.
782 8. Pruned away.
783 9. Assert: primValue is not an Object.
784 10. Return ? ToNumber(primValue).
785 2. If number is not finite or number is either +0 or -0, Return +0.
786 3. Let int be truncate(R(number)).
787 4. Let int32bit be int modulo 232.
788 5. If int32bit ≥ 231, ReturnF(int32bit - 232); otherwise ReturnF(int32bit).
  
```

Figure 2. Algorithm in §7.1.6 of ECMA-262 as projected in the IDE twin. The user added a tag to the algorithm, as well as highlighted and pruned some of the steps. The pseudo-code of the algorithm ToNumber (§7.1.4) has been “inlined”.

The specification document uses the term “step” when referring to a line of an algorithm. Most of the algorithms are “short”: on average, an algorithm has 10 steps.

4.2 An IDE Twin for the ECMA-262 Standard Library Algorithms

We implemented an IDE twin for the standard library algorithms of the *16th edition of the ECMA-262 specification document*⁹ using language workbench JetBrains MPS [49].

The two main languages are L_{262} (the pseudo-code formalism used in the ECMA-262 specification document) and L_{nav} (the navigation DSL described in Section 3.2).

The L_{262} language. MPS concepts in the L_{262} language correspond to constructs used in the algorithmic notation of the ECMA-262 document. The root concept is an *algorithm*, which can be comprised of multiple *steps*. While the ECMA-262 document does not explicitly—nor exhaustively—specify all possible kinds of steps (i.e., the language constructs themselves), independent characterizations exist [22, 83]. Our definition of L_{262} in MPS follows, with some modifications, the work on ESMeta [83].

For MPS concepts that represent constructs of L_{262} , we define a projection that mimics the formatting (syntax highlighting, font attributes, etc.) of the ECMA-262 document (see Figure 2). The projectional nature of MPS [112] enables a uniform enforcing of the diverse set of stylistic conventions defined in the ECMA-262 document. For example, the document has explicit requirements for how nested steps in an algorithm should be numbered [23, Sect. 5.2]. To implement

⁹Ecma International releases new editions of the ECMA-262 document on a yearly basis. The 16th edition is the most recent edition of the standard, published in June 2025.

this in MPS, we define a generic EDITOR COMPONENT that computes and displays the number of a step based on its position in a (nested) AST node; we then reuse this component across EDITOR definitions of all the *step* concepts.

To import the algorithms from the ECMA-262 document into our tool¹⁰, we extend an existing parser from the ES-*Meta* framework [83], which was designed to operate on the ECMA-262 document. Our modification of the ESMeta parser produces a syntax tree in JSON format, which we augment with meta-information about the location of the algorithms in the ECMA-262 document; we retrieve this information from a separate artifact [24] maintained by the TC39 committee. We then specify how nodes from the tree produced by ESMeta should map to MPS nodes in L_{262} programs. This extra layer accounts for a possibility of a future change of the tree format produced by (our extension of) ESMeta. We provide an MPS plugin that imports the standard library algorithms from the ECMA-262 document into the IDE twin.

The IDE twin organizes ECMA-262 algorithms into virtual packages in the outline view of the editor; this mirrors the “Table of Contents” of the normative specification document. Each algorithm is projected in a fully interactive editor with the usual features (go to definition, find usages, renaming, diff, etc.) In addition, each algorithm has a clickable link to the normative specification document. We employ the MPS *Inspector* window to project navigation annotations (e.g., remarks). Thanks to the built-in support of the version control systems in MPS, readers can share their navigation sessions with other readers. In addition, MPS allows creating a URL for any AST node in a document.

The IDE twin supports inlining (cf. “peeking”) the pseudo-code of an algorithm, which is referenced from within another algorithm, directly in the projection of that latter algorithm. This procedure can be applied *ad infinitum*, and it lets users explore an algorithm that calls other algorithms—which in their turn call other algorithms—in a single code editor in the IDE. This is where the projectional editor of MPS is especially useful: nested “frames” have a local scope, and a reader is still able to navigate within it. Unlike “peeking” in VSCode, the “inlining” in our tool is persistent.

The projectional editor of MPS allows changing the concrete syntax of the pseudo-code notation in a straightforward way. This enables several advanced features in the IDE twin, which would be otherwise non-trivial to implement.

First, we can automatically enforce various *editorial conventions*, for example, a change of the indentation style, a new scheme for numbering algorithm steps, a new notation for certain constructs of the pseudo-code language.

Second, we can adapt the presentation of the specification document to various categories of readers. One representative example of this is the notation `? OperationName()`,

¹⁰We note that a manual input of 1101 algorithms into our tool would be impractical.

which is a shorthand for `ReturnIfAbrupt(OperationName());`; the question mark symbol is a point of confusion for specification readers [35]. In the IDE twin, we have implemented an MPS “editor hint” [49] that allows replacing (i.e., re-projecting) the normative shorthand notation with the more verbose version. This operation is directly available for a reader from the context menu.

Third, we observe that the same MPS mechanism could be used to support localization [97] of pseudo-code of the specification document, i.e., by defining a projection for every desired locale.

The L_{nav} language. The projection of a navigation task is split into two parts: the code itself and the report that will be produced as a result of executing the task, when the reader clicks the “Run” button (see Figure 3). Various quickfixes (e.g., “toggle the negation of a filtering template”) and validations (e.g., showing an error message when attempting to specify a non-existing document as the input of a task) aim at facilitating the editing experience of our DSL.

Perhaps the most beneficial use of the MPS projectional editor in the IDE twin is projecting the contains-clauses in filter-blocks. As explained in Section 3.2, a contains-clause specifies a template AST (i.e., an AST with with holes) which is used to filter algorithms whose bodies’ AST contain this template¹¹. A user can thus utilize the pseudo-code notation of the specification document when specifying such templates. We showcase this in Figure 3.

Executing a navigation task creates a copy¹² of the specification document where only algorithms that match the filtering templates are present. Executing a task additionally attaches decorations, performs code editor actions, and generates a report on these algorithms, as specified in the DSL code. Users can also perform these manipulations manually.

We note that having a DSL to express navigation tasks allows users to persist them, and thus utilize the standard IDE functionality, such as, for example, *go to definition*, *diff*, and so on. Moreover, reports generated by executing navigation tasks also are persisted, and thus the usual IDE functionality is applicable to them too.

Exposing the AST of the specification document. While our DSL aims at providing an adequate—to a known extent—support of various navigation-related manipulations, the

¹¹Our implementation of this is a simplification of [39], adapted for MPS. Denote by $n \sqsubseteq p$ the fact that subject node n matches pattern node p . If $\text{conceptOf}(n) \prec \text{conceptOf}(p)$ does not hold, then $n \not\sqsubseteq p$. If it holds, and p is an abstract concept or $p = \text{null}$, then $n \sqsubseteq p$. Assume now that p is not an abstract concept and $p \neq \text{null}$. To determine whether $n \sqsubseteq p$, we need to establish whether this relation holds for MPS “properties”, “children”, and “references” of p and n . For properties, this relation is equality. For children, it is defined inductively on the structure of the node (with some special treatment for cardinalities and null nodes). For references, the relation is defined in terms of whether their resolutions match.

¹²Having a copy of the specification document per navigation task allows users to freely manipulate—even in a destructive manner—this copy.

3 results found.

	Section Number	Section ID	Function Name
#1	20.1.2.1	sec-object.assign	Object.assign
#2	20.1.2.3.1	sec-objectdefineproperties	ObjectDefineProperties
#3	20.1.2.13	sec-object.groupby	Object.groupBy

Figure 3. A navigation task that matches algorithms that have a *for-each* loop with a *let*-step inside. A copy of the specification document is created, and the matching steps are highlighted. Each of the matching algorithms is opened in a new editor tab. The report lists the matching algorithms in ascending order of their corresponding section numbers.

more experienced users may want to express queries that would require more than the current expressive power of our DSL. To allow for this, we expose the abstract syntax tree of the specification document to the users, and they can perform arbitrary manipulations on it, by writing MPS *BaseLanguage* code in the MPS built-in *Read-Eval-Print-Loop* window. We showcase an example of this in Figure 4. □

Thus, the IDE twin that we implemented supports all of the features described in Section 2 of this paper.

4.3 Navigating the Standard Library of ECMA-262

We now give examples of how our DSL can be used.

In the first example, we define a navigation task that finds all algorithms that specify the behaviour of the `toString` methods of the standard JavaScript objects. We add a tag to each of these algorithms, and script the IDE to open them in the code editor. We also produce a report with a sorted list of of these methods and information about their total amount. In our DSL, this can be done as follows.

```
1 navigation Find_prototype.toString
2   input-document ECMA-262
3   output-document result1
4   filter: signature
5     name ".*\..prototype\..toString"
6     number-of-params 0
9
```

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Figure 4. Manipulating the AST of the specification document using MPS *BaseLanguage*. This code finds all steps of the form `Set \square_1 to $\square_1 + \square$` . These steps are shown in a separate MPS pane (to the right) and are not persistent.

```

10007 decorate: add-tag "string-related"
10018 code-editor: open-all in-separate-tabs
10029 report: count, sort-by-section-number

```

In the second example, the navigation task finds all algorithms that have so-called “non-normative” steps [23], i.e., assertions or comments in the algorithms. We add the prefix “NON_NORMATIVE_” to the names of these algorithms (these new names will then be used everywhere across the copy of the specification document), and group them together in the outline view. The non-normative steps become highlighted. This can be specified as follows in our DSL.

```

10121 navigation Find_Non_Normative_Steps
10132 input-document ECMA-262
10143 output-document result2
10154 filter: body
10165     either contains [Assert:  $\square$ ]
10176     or contains [NOTE:  $\square$ ]
10187 decorate: highlight #ffff00
10208 code-editor:
10219     rename "NON_NORMATIVE_"
10220     put-into-folder "NonNormativeSteps"
10231 report: sort-by-number-of-params

```

In the third example, we find all algorithms where a list access expression can appear in a step, and highlight such steps. Here we use a *fragment* of a step as the filtering pattern.

```

10281 navigation Find_List_Accesses
10292 input-document ECMA-262
10303 output-document result3
10314 filter: body contains [ $\square[\square]$ ]
10325 decorate: highlight #ffff00
10336

```

Performing this navigation task on the original HTML specification document would be complicated: textual search with a regular expression yields false positives.

In the final example, we intend to find all algorithms that contain a set-step of the form `Set \square_1 to $\square_1 + \square$` . Here the name of the assigned variable and the name of the variable mentioned in the left term of the addition expression should be the same. While expressing this query in our DSL is not directly possible, a user can manipulate the AST of the pseudo-code (that we expose in the IDE twin) by using the MPS *BaseLanguage*, and perform this query (see Figure 4).

Unlike the navigation tasks expressed in our DSL, neither this query nor its results are persisted. The user can, however, manually add decorations to the matched steps. \square

5 Related Work

Code navigation and comprehension have been extensively explored in the literature. Ko et al. [59] present a catalogue of information that developers use during code navigation. Storey [94] and Brooks [10] discuss program comprehension from the cognitive perspective. Crosby and Stelovsky [15] explore how different code reading strategies influence comprehension of algorithmic prose. Robillard et al. [79] report on factors related to code investigation behaviour.

Multiple authors have explored how tooling can support code navigation and comprehension (e.g., [62, 95]). Bragdon et al. [9] and Henley and Fleming [38] explore representing code as a collection of editable fragments; our approach follows a “traditional” IDE layout. Murphy et al. [74] discuss on how developers use features of the Eclipse IDE. Several approaches are known to employ dynamic information in code navigation (e.g., [54, 58, 82]), which we do not focus on. Shakil et al. [86] describe how eye tracking can be used for code navigation.

Cheng et al. [11] advocate for integrating collaboration into IDEs as a first-class citizen. Zhang [121] presents a tool that records navigation and configuration history of IDE states, and van Deursen et al. [110] employ similar information to improve collaboration between developers. Leon [65] discusses collaboration in code navigation from the perspective of the information foraging theory. Begel and DeLine [7] discuss how features of social networks can be incorporated in the development process. In our work, collaboration is possible via the version control system support by MPS (users can persist navigation tasks and their results).

There is an ample amount of literature on code querying and searching. Lee et al. [63] discuss how code search can be integrated in the development process. Liu et al. [67] and Di Grazia and Pradel [20] present surveys on code search techniques. Urma and Mycroft [109] identify relevant characteristics of code query languages. Janzen and De Volder [47] present a code browsing tool with a built-in logic query language; their system also supports persisting exploration paths during code search. Syrel et al. [98] and Johnson and Simha [50] explore composable tools and languages for code querying. Balachandran [5] and Bartman et al. [6] present syntax-aware query languages. Persistence of queries and their results, query composition, and syntax-aware queries are all supported in our approach.

While the filtering mechanism we described in Section 3 focuses on the syntactic (structural) querying, other approaches are possible. Verbaere et al. [111] and Spoon and Shivers [91] present systems for semantically navigating Java and Smalltalk code, respectively. Zimmer and Rauschmayer [122] explore

ontology-based code navigation and annotation. Kimmig et al. [56] discuss code querying with natural language queries.

Paul and Prakash [78] introduce an algebraic language to model source code query systems. Güting et al. [36] present an algebra for structured documents. Dau and Sifer [17] describe a formalism for navigating XML documents.

The code editing actions described in Section 3.2 could be thought of as a mechanism of scripting an IDE. Fabry et al. [29] introduce a DSL to manipulate IDE events in the style of aspect-oriented programming. Jeanjean et al. [48] discuss manipulating IDEs using LSP-like protocols.

Mosses [72] explores hyperlinked *twins* that provide web-based navigable representations of language definitions. Thus, IDE *twins* introduced in Section 2 represent the “other direction” of Mosses’ approach. We mention a recent work by Michael et al. [70] who discuss the role of digital *twins* in model-driven development.

Choe et al. [12] present an HTML-based tool to visualize the execution of the algorithms from the ECMA-262 specification when run on sample JavaScript code snippets. While their approach is aimed at observing the effects of *executing* the algorithms’ pseudo-code (where the pseudo-code is still shown as HTML text), our approach focuses on providing IDE support for *reading* and *navigating* the pseudo-code itself.

Klusener and Zaytsev [57] advocate for tool support in programming language standardization. Our work is an implementation of one of the items (“generate browsable versions of the language standard”) of their agenda.

6 Discussion

In principle, an IDE twin for a language specification document can also be used for *authoring new algorithms*: all the projections defined for reading the pseudo-code can be used “out-of-the-box” for writing it. In our current implementation, such editing would however be cumbersome because of the well-known issues with projectional editors (e.g., linear input of tree structures) [112]. While these issues can be fully mitigated in MPS [113], we chose not to focus on the writing aspect—since the scope of our work is to enable *reading and navigating* the specification document (reading is supposedly done by significantly more users than writing—the latter being a prerogative of language design teams).

An IDE twin for a language specification document can thus be thought of as a “reading-first IDE”. The pseudo-code loaded into the IDE twin from an existing (and supposedly correct) specification document is assumed to be correct-by-construction—or rather, “correct-by-import”. The pseudo-code is only updated (i.e., re-imported) once the *design team* of a programming language releases a new edition of the specification document. In case of the ECMA-262 specification, for instance, this happens once a year.

We describe now how the reading- and navigation-related functionality of an IDE twin of a programming language specification document can be used to inform the *evolution* of that programming language. We elaborate on the case study we presented in Section 4 and the evolution process of the JavaScript language.

When discussing new suggestions (so-called “*proposals*”) for the JavaScript language, the TC39 committee follows a six-stage process [101]. Each of the stages **0**, **1**, **2**, **2.7**, **3**, and **4** represents an increasing level of maturity of a proposal, ranging from “a new idea” to “a new feature incorporated in the ECMA-262 specification document”¹³. A proposal matures the most during the stages **2**, **2.7**, and **3** of the process. In particular, stage **2.7** requires the specification text of a proposal to be finalized. Between stages **2** and **2.7** of the process, the committee assigns *reviewers* who verify whether the candidate specification text conforms to the established “style” and “ethos” (neither of which is explicitly defined) in which the rest of the specification document is written. Once a proposal is at stage **2.7**, no further changes to the candidate specification text are allowed. At stage **2.7**, the committee develops a testing suite for the proposal, and once that is done, the proposal reaches stage **3**, where implementors (i.e., major browser engines and other JavaScript execution environments) start implementing—and preliminary shipping—the proposal. Ordinary JavaScript developers have traditionally perceived stage **3** proposals as “almost done” language features [101], and many developers adopt these proposals early in their codebases [100]. This happens even before a proposal reaches stage **4**, the requirement for which is a presence of two independent implementations and an in-the-field experience with the proposal. This means that once a proposal reaches stage **3**, it becomes very difficult for the language committee to revert it to a lower stage. And, since the specification text has been fixed at stage **2.7**, the reviewing process that happens between stages **2** and **2.7** makes a significant impact on the proposal and its implementations.

Most of the new proposals that the TC39 has considered in the past 5 years are additions to the standard library of the language (rather than additions to the language syntax), and this trend is expected to continue, as can be seen from the minutes of the past committee meetings [100]. Thus, in most cases, the reviewing process of a proposal consists of ensuring that the specification of a new algorithm “conforms to” the specification of rest of the algorithms in the standard library. This includes, for example, checking for consistency with similar methods on other built-in objects, consistency of naming of local variables, methods, arguments, consistency of error handling, reuse of existing abstract operations,

¹³Once a part of the specification, a feature cannot be removed from the language, since backwards-compatibility plays a crucial rôle in the evolution of JavaScript [100, 101].

and so on. Proposal reviewers thus have to navigate the specification document to locations that will help them give an informed feedback on the proposal. This is where the navigation-related functionality of the IDE twin is especially useful: reviewers would benefit from the structural search (e.g., when searching for similar places in the specification text), from adding tags and remarks to locations of interest, from decorating (e.g., highlighting or pruning) steps of individual algorithms, from invoking code editor actions to bulk-manipulate relevant algorithms, from generating reports on algorithms that satisfy the search criteria. Reviewers would also benefit from sharing their navigation sessions with other reviewers or authors of the proposal, who could then get—in a reproducible manner—concrete examples that motivated the reviewers’ feedback on the proposal.

We expect this user group to be well-versed in the notion of abstract syntax trees; they can thus benefit from the MPS-level query language to perform arbitrary manipulation of the specification document AST.

We also note that the IDE twin supports¹⁴ *time navigation* (cf. [1, 64]). It is possible to import multiple (previous) versions of the ECMA-262 document, and use the navigation-related functionality *across* these documents (e.g., diffing two versions of the same algorithm [26]). This is useful for language implementors when identifying the necessary modifications to their current language implementation after a new version of the language specification has been released [92].

7 Conclusion and Future Work

In this work, we identified a collection of possible features for IDE twins of programming language specification documents, and presented a feature model for them. To the best of our knowledge, we presented a first implementation of an *IDE twin* for a specification document of a *major industrial programming language*.

We presented a formal definition of a *navigation-aware* programming language specification document, and introduced one of the first *pseudo-code navigation languages*. In addition to the notation-aware structural search on specification documents, the DSL allows expressing manipulations on these documents and their code editors. Our approach can be thought of as “code navigation as code”, where both the navigation tasks and their results can be persisted and worked with in an IDE as first-class citizens.

We demonstrated the feasibility of our approach on the standard library algorithms of the JavaScript language specification, whose pseudo-code accounts for more than 50% of the pages of the normative 847-page PDF document. We also

¹⁴This support is however somewhat limited, since the pseudo-code formalism itself has evolved (cf. [120]) over time [117], and the import process in our tool is based on an external ECMA-262 parser [83] which, in its turn, is tailored for certain versions of that formalism.

discussed the relevance of our approach for the *evolution process* of the JavaScript language.

One possible direction for future work is to extend the expressive power of the navigation DSL, and introduce parameterized (“generic”) navigation tasks, filtering templates, decorating actions, code editing actions, and aggregating actions. This would allow reuse of the code written in our DSL; one can then define libraries of navigation tasks, templates, and actions.

Another direction for future work is to integrate our tool with ESMeta [83]; this would allow visualizing the results of static code analysis (e.g., type information) and code execution directly in our tool [12].

The IDE twin we implemented *enables* navigation-related functionality in the ECMA-262 specification document. In-the-field experience and future empirical studies should explore large-scale applicability of our approach in the context of the TC39 committee work, as described in Section 6. A broader study would compare the usability of IDE twins across specification documents of other software languages.

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A Appendix: Machinery of Navigation Tasks

We describe here the machinery of the constituents of a navigation task.

Filtering templates. In a most general setting, the machinery of filtering templates can be defined as follows. Consider Boolean predicates representing filtering templates of the four kinds discussed in Section 3.

For a template f_i in the location-sub-block, a predicate $\mathfrak{P}_i(\{\text{title, number, id}\}, U)$ is true if the title, number, or identifier of the structural unit U match the regular expressions defined in title, number, and id, respectively. In this case, the filtering template will match all algorithms in the specification document which reside in such structural unit.

For a template f_i in the annotations-sub-block, a predicate $\mathfrak{P}_i(d, \Omega)$ is true if $\exists \omega \in \Omega$ which is represented by the decorating action d . Again, all algorithms for which this holds, will match the filtering template.

For a template f_i in the signature-sub-block, a predicate $\mathfrak{P}_i(p, \sigma)$ is true if the signature σ satisfies the property p . Again, all algorithms for which this is true, will match the filtering template.

Finally, for a template f_i in the body-sub-block, a predicate $\mathfrak{P}_i(C_{[\circ]}, C)$ will be true if the abstract syntax tree C of an algorithm matches the abstract syntax tree with holes $C_{[\circ]}$ specified in the template, i.e., $C \sqsubseteq C_{[\circ]}$ (see footnote 11). All algorithms for which this is true will match the filtering template.

The machinery of a filter-block $N_{\text{filter}} = \bigwedge_j (f_1^j \vee \dots \vee f_{t_j}^j)$ is then defined as a conjunction of the form

$$\bigwedge_j (\mathfrak{P}_1^j \vee \dots \vee \mathfrak{P}_{t_j}^j),$$

where a predicate \mathfrak{P}_i^j represents a filtering template f_i^j .

Decorating actions. The machinery of a decorating action can be formalized in terms of the changes it introduces to the set Ω of navigation annotations. For instance, the machinery of the add-tag decorating action can be expressed as follows:

$$\text{add-tag}(s, \widehat{E}) : \Omega \mapsto \Omega \cup \{\langle \text{TAG}(s), @e \rangle\}$$

Here $s \in \text{String}$ represents the label of the tag, and $e \in \widehat{E}$, with $\widehat{E} \subset \{\sigma\} \cup E$, represents a target to where the tag is attached (either the algorithm's signature σ or a step from the set E of targets that match the filtering templates in the filter-block). The navigation annotation is attached to all targets $e \in \widehat{E}$.

Code editor actions. The machinery of code editor actions can be defined in terms of their effect on the code editor state Θ of the IDE twin. For instance, the open-all editor action calls the IDE command `OpenEditor` with an argument $e \in \widehat{E}$ representing a subset of algorithms of the specification document that match the filtering templates from the filter-block:

$$\text{open-all}(\widehat{E}) : \Theta \mapsto \Theta \circ \{e \in \widehat{E} \subseteq \mathcal{A}_{\text{in}} \mid \text{OpenEditor}(e)\}$$

Similarly, the put-into-folder editor action executes the IDE command `MoveTo`, which moves each target algorithm $e \in \widehat{E}$ into a folder with name $s \in \text{String}$:

$$\text{put-into-folder}(s, \widehat{E}) : \Theta \mapsto \Theta \circ \{e \in \widehat{E} \subseteq \mathcal{A}_{\text{in}} \mid \text{MoveTo}(e, s)\}$$